

UKBOL BUFFER AND REAGENT PREP SOP

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A guide to preparing all buffers and reagents to run the UKBOL Accelerated lab pipeline.

A. EXTRACTION BUFFERS PREPARATION:

1. Consumables and Reagents

Extraction Consumables	Provider	Cat #
Kingfisher Deep Well Plates	Thermofisher	95040460B
Kingfisher Tip Comb (Deep Well)	Thermofisher	97002524B
Kingfisher Wide Well Plates (200 μ L)	Thermofisher	97002540B

Extraction Reagents	Provider	Cat #
2-propanol	Sigma Aldrich	59304-500ML-F
EDTA (0.5M)	Invitrogen	15575020
Guanidine hydrochloride	Sigma Aldrich	G3272-1KG
MagAttract Suspension G	Qiagen	1026901
Proteinase K	Thermofisher	EO0492
Sodium acetate (3M)	Thermofisher	AM9740
Tris-HCl (1M, pH8)	Invitrogen	15568025
Tween 20	Teknova	T0710

NOTE: ensure bottles and measuring cylinders have been autoclaved before starting reagent prep.

2. **Lysis Buffer C** – Store in fridge

200mM Tris pH8, 25mM EDTA pH8, 0.05% (vol/vol) Tween 20, 0.4mg/ml PK

Reagent	1x plate
Water	7295 μ L
Tris (1M, pH8)	2000 μ L
EDTA (0.5M)	500 μ L
Tween 20	5 μ L
Proteinase K (20mg/mL)	200 μ L *
	10 mL

* Can make up in 15 mL tubes with all components except PK. When prepping tubes for extraction simply add 200 μ L PK, vortex well and aliquot 90 μ L into the strip tubes.

3. **Elution Buffer (EB)** – Store in fridge

10mM Tris pH8, 1mM EDTA pH8, 0.05% (vol/vol) Tween 20

Reagent	Vol (10 plates)
Water	49.4 mL
Tris (1M, pH8)	500 µL
EDTA (0.5M)	100 µL
Tween 20	25 µL
	50 mL

3.1. Pre-prepare elution plates using the Integra Viaflow. Add 50 uL per well to Kingfisher Wide Well plates and place in fridge until needed.

4. **Binding Buffer D** – Store in fridge (max 4 weeks)

5 M guanidine hydrochloride, 40% (vol/vol) 2-propanol, 0.12 M sodium acetate and 0.05% (vol/vol) Tween 20

4.1. Weigh **124.2 g of guanidine hydrochloride**

4.2. Fill molecular grade water to around **150 mL**

4.3. Briefly heat in microwave in short bursts until all the salt is fully dissolved (use hand heat protectors)

4.4. Then add the following reagents to the bottle:

Reagent	Vol (6x plates)
2-propanol	104 mL
Sodium acetate (3M, pH 5.2)	10.4 mL
Tween 20	130 µL
	265 mL

4.5. Seal bottle with parafilm and store in the fridge until needed

5. **Wash Buffer** - Store in fridge

10mM Tris pH8, 80% (vol/vol) ethanol

Reagent	Vol (~7x plates)
Water	83 mL
Tris-HCl (1M, pH 8.0)	5 mL
Molecular grade ethanol	412 mL
	500 mL

5.1. Seal bottle with parafilm and store in the fridge until needed.

NOTE: Binding Buffer D, Wash Buffer and Elution Buffer can be added to the Kingfisher plates using the Integra Viaflow. Plates can be batch prepared the week of the extraction and kept sealed in the fridge until needed.

B. LIBRARY PREPARATION BUFFERS AND REAGENTS:

6. Consumables and Reagents

Library Prep Consumables	Provider	Cat #
Hard-Shell® 96-Well PCR Plates, low profile, thin wall, skirted, white/white	Bio Rad	#HSP9665
iDOT tubes	Dispendix	D16110027286
Integra tips	Integra	6475/6434
Kingfisher Tip Comb (thin)	ThermoFisher	97002560
MicroAmp™ optical adhesive film	Applied Biosystems	4311971
Rainin tips	FisherSci	17010645

Reagent	Provider	Cat #
10X T4 RNA Ligase Buffer	NEB	B0216L
10x rCutSmart Buffer	NEB	B6004S
Amplitaq Gold 360 Master Mix	Fisher Scientific	10289234
AMPureXP Reagent	Beckman Coulter	A63880
ATP (100 mM)	Thermo Scientific	R0441
Cytiva Sera-Mag™ SpeedBead	Cytiva	GE45152105050250
DTT (1 M)	Thermo Scientific	P2325
EDTA pH 8.0 (0.5M)	Invitrogen	15575020
ET SSB (500 ng/μL)	NEB	M2401S
Glycerol (50%)	Invitrogen	15514011
KCl (1M)	Sigma-Aldrich	60142-100ML-F
LUNA SYBR qPCR Master Mix	NEB	M3003E
MgCl ₂ (1M)	Invitrogen	AM9530G
NaCl (5M)	Sigma-Aldrich	S5150-1L
PEG 8000 (50%)	Sigma-Aldrich	89510
SYBR Green (10 000X)	Invitrogen	10710004
T4 DNA Ligase (2,000,000 U/mL)	NEB	M0202M
T4 PNK (10,000 U/mL)	NEB	M0201L
Tris-HCl pH 8.0 (1M)	Invitrogen	15568025
Tween-20 (10%)	Teknova	T0710

7. TE Buffer – Store in fridge (Used to resuspend lyophilized i5/i7 indexes and for SPRI bead preparation)

10 mM Tris-HCl (pH 8.0), 1 mM EDTA (pH 8.0)

	Starting conc	Final conc	Vol (many plates)
Water			49.4 mL
Tris-HCl	1 M	10 mM	500 μL
EDTA	0.5 M	1 mM	100 μL
			50 mL

8. **EBT Buffer** – Store in fridge (Used during AL bead cleans)

10 mM Tris-HCl (pH 8.0), 0.05% Tween-20

	Starting conc	Final conc	Vol (10 plates)
Water			49.475 mL
Tris-HCl	1 M	10 mM	500 µL
Tween-20		0.05%	25 µL
			50 mL

9. **18% PEG SPRI Beads** - Store in the fridge covered with foil (Used for post-AL cleans). Limit the number of thaw cycles.

9.1. Wash Beads:

- 9.1.1. Mix SpeedBeads until all beads are in suspension.
- 9.1.2. Transfer 1 mL of SpeedBeads to a 2.0 mL Eppendorf tube.
- 9.1.3. Place tube on a magnetic rack and allow beads to fully concentrate (~1 min).
- 9.1.4. While on the magnetic rack discard the supernatant.
- 9.1.5. Add 1 mL of TE (10mM Tris, 1mM EDTA) to the tube.
- 9.1.6. Cap tube and remove from the rack, then fully resuspend the beads by vortexing.
- 9.1.7. Place tube on the magnetic rack and allow beads to fully concentrate (~1 min).
- 9.1.8. While on the magnetic rack discard the supernatant.
- 9.1.9. Repeat wash steps 1.5 – 1.8 for a second wash.
- 9.1.10. Add 1 mL of TE to the tube, resuspend beads by vortexing.

9.2. 18% SPRI Preparation:

- 9.2.1. Add 9 g of PEG-8000 powder to a 50 mL tube.
- 9.2.2. Add the following to the tube:
- 9.2.3. 10 mL of 5M NaCl,
- 9.2.4. 500 µL 1M Tris-HCl
- 9.2.5. 100 µL 0.5M EDTA
- 9.2.6. Add UltraPure water to the 50 mL tube up to ~49 mL.
- 9.2.7. Cap the 50 mL tube, then shake or rotate until PEG has completely dissolved.
- 9.2.8. Add 27.5 µL of Tween-20 to the 50 mL tube.
- 9.2.9. Add the 1 mL of washed SpeedBeads to the 50 mL tube.
- 9.2.10. Fill with UltraPure water to the 50 mL line of the 50 mL tube.
- 9.2.11. Gently shake until SpeedBeads are mixed.
- 9.2.12. Wrap 50mL tube in foil and store in the dark at 4°C.

9.3. Additionally, the beads can be pre-diluted with EBT ahead of the adapter ligation clean step. Label “**EBT + SPRI**”. Wrap 50mL tube in foil and store at 4°C.

	100 rxns (1 plate)	500 rxns (5 plates)
18% SPRI Beads	6 mL	30 mL
EBT	3.5 mL	17.5 mL
	9.5 mL	47.5 mL

10. SSB Preparation

10.1. SSB Dilution Buffer – Store at -20°C (Used to dilute SSB)

10 mM Tris-HCl pH 8.0, 100 mM KCl, 0.1 mM EDTA, 50% Glycerol

	Vol
1 M Tris-HCl	20 µL
2 M KCl	0.4 µL
0.5 M EDTA	200 µL
Glycerol 100%	1000 µL
Water	779.6 µL
	2000 µL

10.2. SSB Dilutions – Store at -20°C. (Stable for at least 2 months).

10.2.1. Make a dilution of ET SSB (NEB (M2401S), to 60.8 ng/µL

	1 plate (100 rxns)	2 plates (200 rxns)
ET SSB (500 ng/µL)	15.2 µL	30.4 µL
SSB Dilution Buffer	84.8 µL	169.6 µL
EBT	25 µL	50 µL
	125 µL	250 µL

NOTE: The final glycerol content of the SSB dilutions must be below 43% as that is the maximum threshold for the IDOT.

11. Adapter Splints

All oligonucleotides are IDT Format (5' → 3') and ordered desalted from IDT. Order multiple batches and see oligonucleotide control recommendations detailed in original protocol by Kapp *et al* 2021.

scr_P5_adapter	/5AmMC12/ACACTCTTTCCCTACACGACGCTCTTCCGATCT
scr_P7_adapter	/5Phos/AGATCGGAAGAGCACACGTCTGAACTCCAGTCAC/3AmMO/
scr_P5_splint	/5AmMC6/NNNNNNNAGATCGGAAGAGCGTCGTGTAGGGAAAGAGTGT/3AmMO/
scr_P7_splint	/5AmMC12/GTGACTGGAGTTCAGACGTGTGCTCTTCCGATCTNNNNNNN/3AmMO/

11.1. Adapter Splint Hybridization:

11.1.1. Resuspend all oligonucleotides to 100 μM using TE buffer.

11.1.2. Add the following components to two 0.2 mL tubes:

P5	
Water	30.6 μL
100 μM scr_P5_adapter	6 μL
100 μM scr_P5_splint	8.4 μL
10X T4 RNA Ligase Buffer	5 μL
	50 μL

P7	
Water	30.6 μL
100 μM scr_P7_adapter	6 μL
100 μM scr_P7_splint	8.4 μL
10X T4 RNA Ligase Buffer	5 μL
	50 μL

11.1.3. In a thermocycler with heated lid (105 $^{\circ}\text{C}$), hybridize the adapters and splints by incubating at 95 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 3 minutes before ramping down to 10 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ at 0.1 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ per second.

11.1.4. Store hybridized P5 (12 μM) and P7 (12 μM) adapter stock solutions at -20 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and freeze / thaw no more than 3 times.

11.1.5. Dilute adapter stocks with a 1:10 dilution of 10x rCutSmart buffer

11.1.6. P5 adapter/splint from **12 μM** to **2 μM**

P5 (12 μM)	33.4 μL
1x Cutsmart Buffer	166.6 μL
	100 μL

11.1.7. P7 adapter/splint from **12 μM** to **0.4 μM**

P7 (12 μM)	3.3 μL
1x Cutsmart Buffer	96.7 μL
	100 μL

11.1.8. Make up aliquots of 100 μL in 8-strips (100 μL should be

11.1.9. Store hybridized P5 and P7 adapter/splints separately at -20 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and freeze/thaw dilutions no more than 3 times.

12. Reaction Mix – Store at -20 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. (Freeze/thaw no more than 3 times. Reaction mix is stable for at least 2 months.)

	X1 rxn (μL)	Final Conc. in Rxn Vol	X100 rxns (μL) (1x plate)
50% PEG 8000	9.20	18.3%	920
1M Tris	1.25	50 mM	125
1M MgCl₂	0.25	10 mM	25
1M DTT	0.25	10 mM	25
100mM ATP	0.25	1 mM	25
T4 PNK	0.55	0.22 U/ μL	55
T4 DNA Ligase	0.25	20 U/ μL	25
			1200

- Heat 50% PEG 8000 to 55°C prior to pipetting and then cool on ice for 1 min (to get to RT) before adding the remaining reaction mix reagents
- While at room temperature mix by flicking for 30 seconds, spin down. Afterwards, pulse vortex at least 5 times for 3s each pulse, spin down and repeat twice more.
- **Final PEG conc. for reaction mix is 39% (50% * 9.2/11.75)**

Reaction mix is made in advance and plated out in skirted plates using the Integra Viaflow, each well containing enough for 4 uses, plus overage (reaction mix is very viscous).

13. Amplitaq + SYBR green

- 13.1. A 1/100 dilution of SYBR green can be made using sterile water
- 13.2. Add the following together and vortex thoroughly:

	1x rxn	1x plates (100 rxns)
Amplitaq Gold	24.87 µL	2487.5 µL
SYBR Green (1/100)	0.125 µL	12.5 µL
	25 µL	2500 µL

- 13.3. The combined Amplitaq and SYBR can be added to the IconPCR plates using the Integra Viaflow (12.5 µL per well).
- 13.4. The plate should be sealed with a foil seal to prevent light exposure and light degradation to the SYBR and stored in the freezer at -20°C until needed for indexing PCR.
- 13.5. Label the plate with place to fill in the following information:
- UK_____
 - Index _____
 - DNA Added?
- 13.6. Do not freeze/thaw more than 2 times.